

Cannabidiol in the Treatment of Animal Models of Schizophrenia: a Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

The current antipsychotics used in the treatment of schizophrenia display several collateral effects, and minimum benefits to cognitive commitment. As the second major component of Cannabis sativa, the cannabidiol exhibited an antipsychotic profile in rodents and humans. The present research had the objective to provide an updated review of the animal used to evaluate the cannabidiol antipsychotic effects in the models of schizophrenia. A bibliographic research was performed using electronic databases (Medline, Science Direct, Lilacs, and BVS) to preclinical articles of research, published in English in the period of January 2010 and February 2020. The descriptors used were schizophrenia, schizophrenia spectrum and other psychotic disorders, paranoid schizophrenia, disorganized schizophrenia, childhood schizophrenia, catatonic schizophrenia, cannabidiol. Initially, the search strategy resulted in a total of 235 articles. After a selection to exclude the duplicated and not accessible articles, a total of 106 selected articles remained to the initial screening by title and subtitle. As a result of the initial and the full-text screenings, only 15 articles were included in this review. The cannabidiol revealed, both in behavioral and biochemical trials, the existence of an antipsychotic effect, acting in a different pathway, compared to other antipsychotics, especially in higher doses, as 30 and 60 mg/kg. However, further studies are necessary for understanding the possible mechanism of action of this effect.

Additional keywords: Laboratory animals; Mental Disorders; Psychopharmacology; Medicinal plants.

RESUMO

Cannabidiol no Tratamento de Animais Modelos de Schizophrenia: Uma Revisão de Literatura

Os antipsicóticos atuais utilizados no tratamento da esquizofrenia apresentam diversos efeitos colaterais e benefícios mínimos ao comprometimento cognitivo. Como segundo componente principal da Cannabis sativa, o canabidiol exibiu um perfil antipsicótico em roedores e humanos. O objetivo da presente revisão foi obter informações atualizadas sobre o animal utilizado para avaliar os efeitos do antipsicótico canabidiol nos modelos de esquizofrenia. Foi realizada uma pesquisa bibliográfica em bases de dados eletrônicas (Medline, Science Direct, Lilacs e BVS) sobre artigos de pesquisa pré-clínica, publicados no período de janeiro de 2010 a fevereiro de 2020. Os descritores utilizados foram esquizofrenia, espectro da esquizofrenia e outros transtornos psicóticos, esquizofrenia paranoide, esquizofrenia desorganizada, esquizofrenia infantil, esquizofrenia catatônica, canabidiol. Inicialmente, a estratégia de busca resultou num total de 235 artigos, sendo que após a exclusão

dos artigos duplicados e não acessíveis, restaram 106 artigos selecionados para a triagem inicial por título e subtítulo. Como resultado da triagem inicial e do texto completo, apenas 15 artigos foram incluídos nesta revisão. De acordo com os resultados, o canabidiol revelou, tanto em ensaios comportamentais como bioquímicos, um efeito antipsicótico, atuando de forma diferente, em comparação com outros antipsicóticos, especialmente em doses mais elevadas, como 30 e 60 mg/kg. Porém, mais estudos são necessários para compreender o possível mecanismo de ação desse efeito.

Palavras-chave adicionais: Animais de laboratório; Transtornos Mentais; Psicofarmacologia; Plantas medicinais.

INTRODUCTION

According to the data obtained from the 2017 Global Burden of Diseases, Injuries, and Risk Factors (GBD 2017), schizophrenia affects almost 20 million people all over the world. In this disorder, significant neurocognitive decay occurs, affecting up to 75% of the patients. The symptomatology is multifaceted, with the presence of positive symptoms, like hallucinations and delusions, and of negative symptoms, as the lack of pleasure, motivation, affection, and other cognitive deficiencies related to attention, work memory, and executive functions (Batinic, 2007; Dollfus & Lyne, 2016, 2017; White, 2019).

The current antipsychotics used in the treatment of schizophrenia displays several collateral effects, such as motor disorders, and weight gain. They also interfere in the immune system, intestinal microbiota, and in the hormonal secretion, besides having minimum benefits to cognitive commitment (Pillinger *et al.*, 2020; Lobo *et al.*, 2022). Also, the antipsychotics of first and second classes are relatively inefficient in the treatment of symptoms, corroborating with the necessity of new medicaments that provide a better life quality to these patients (Wubshet *et al.*, 2019; Huhn *et al.*, 2019).

The cannabidiol (CBD) was isolated for the first time in 1940 by Adams Roger. Nevertheless, its chemical structure was elucidated only in 1963, by a group from Israeli, Raphael Mechoulam, who determined its stereochemical structure as Delta 9-tetrahydrocannabinol (Δ^9 -THC) in the 1960s (Appendino, 2020). As the second major component of *Cannabis sativa*, the CBD became the focus of several scientific researches for not affecting the motor function, memory, body temperature or inducing addiction after repeated use, besides antagonizing some collateral effects, as the psychoactive, and potentiating some benefits of the Δ^9 -THC (Hudson *et al.*, 2019; Woelfl *et al.*, 2020).

It was observed that users of *C. sativa* have

a higher risk to develop schizophrenia, due to the presence of high doses of Δ^9 -THC. This risk becomes even higher to people predisposed to psychosis (Ortiz-Medina *et al.*, 2018; Pearson & Berry, 2019). Curiously, according to Rohleder (2016), the CBD exhibit an antipsychotic profile in humans and rodents, because of that, the objective of the present article is to provide an updated review of the animal uses to evaluate the cannabidiol antipsychotic effects in the models of schizophrenia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Bibliographic search was performed using electronic databases (Medline, ScienceDirect, Lilacs, and BV5) to preclinical articles of research, published in English, with publishing dates between January 2010 and February 2023. The descriptors used were schizophrenia, schizophrenia spectrum and other psychotic disorders, paranoid schizophrenia, disorganized schizophrenia, childhood schizophrenia, catatonic schizophrenia, cannabidiol. Different search combinations were used according to the requirements or limitations of each database (Table 1).

1 - Inclusion Criteria

The eligible studies to be included in this systematic review must evaluate the effects of CBD in treatment or prevention of schizophrenia in preclinical models, and have been published in Portuguese or English between 2010 and 2020. All the articles were initially selected by title and abstract to guarantee that only studies related to the theme were included. The articles approved in the initial screening were reviewed in full text. Besides that, the duplicated, as the out of criteria articles, were excluded from the research.

2 - Data extraction and analysis

After the screening process, the original research articles that fitted the criteria were reviewed, and

Table 1 - Used combinations for each database

Database	Search Term
Pubmed	("Schizophrenia"[Mesh] OR "Schizophrenia Spectrum and Other Psychotic Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Schizophrenia, Paranoid"[Mesh] OR "Schizophrenia, Disorganized"[Mesh] OR "Schizophrenia, Childhood"[Mesh] OR "Schizophrenia, Catatonic"[Mesh]) AND "Cannabidiol"[Mesh]
BVS Regional Portal	tw:(schizophrenia AND cannabidiol) AND (la:(“en” OR “pt”)) AND (year_cluster: [2010 TO 2020])
Lilacs	“Esquizofrenia” AND “cannabidiol” OR “schizophrenia” and “cannabidiol”
Sciencedirect	“Schizophrenia” AND “cannabidiol”

the following information was extracted: author, publishing year, animal gender, schizophrenia model type, animal species, and administered drugs and dosage. Besides that, were registered, about the intervention of CBD, the doses, frequency, administration pathway, used experimental paradigm, and information relative to the results of treatment and biochemical trial. The detailed information was tabled in Excel. Graphs were developed to demonstrate the most used animal models, information about treatment, and the used trials.

RESULTS

1 - Included studies

Initially, the search strategy resulted in a total of 238 articles (Figure 1). After the exclusion of the duplicated and not accessible articles, 109 selected articles remained to the initial screening by title and subtitle. The review, editorial, and clinical trial articles were excluded, as well as the ones that did not report the use of cannabidiol, and those that did not report the treatment to schizophrenia, resulting in 20 articles to be evaluated. Two were removed from the study for using a CBD derivative and for only a membrane receptor analysis. Only 13 articles and their result were included in this systematic review (Table 2).

2 - Characteristics of selected studies

From the 13 included studies (Almeida *et al.*, 2013; Levin *et al.*, 2014; Gomes *et al.*, 2015a; Gomes *et al.*, 2015b; Deiana *et al.*, 2015; Sonogo *et al.*, 2016; Stark *et al.*, 2019; Osborne *et al.*, 2019a; Jimenez Naranjo *et al.*, 2019; Osborne *et al.*, 2019b; Silva *et al.*, 2020; Kruk-Slomka & Biala, 2021; Visini *et al.*, 2022), animals of different species were used: (1) Sprague-Dawley Rats – rat lineage susceptible

to breast tumors used in research related to toxicology and pharmacology, (2) Wistar Rats-Rat lineage used as a model to toxicology and general biomedical research, (3) spontaneously hypertensive rats (SHR) Rats, (4) C57BL/6J Mice – Isogenic mice (inbred) model to immunology, oncology and toxicology, (5) A/Jarc Mice – used in CD antigen research, antigen receptors and histocompatibility markers, (6) Swiss Mice – used for decades in biomedical research, mainly in pharmacology, and (7) Nrg1 TM HET mice – are genetically modified, used for studies of schizophrenia.

The most used schizophrenia model was induced by dizocilpine (MK-801), being administered in different doses between 0,1 to 1 mg/kg by acute intraperitoneal pathway during a period of 28 days. Other models of schizophrenia used were the SHR rats, induced by polyriboinosinic-polyribocytidylyl (poly I:C), induced by methyl azoxymethanol mitotoxine (MAM) and used genetically modified models Nrg 1 TM HEAT mice, only one article did not use any model to analyze the catalepsy test induced by haloperidol.

The used CBD doses were 1 mg/kg, 3 mg/kg, 5 mg/kg, 10 mg/kg, 12 mg/kg, 15 mg/kg, 30 mg/kg, 50 mg /kg and 60 mg /kg by intraperitoneal pathway. There were different treatment durations: Acute, 4 days, 7 days, 14 days, 20 days, 21 days, 22 days and 30 days, being one or two applications per day.

The behavioral tests used were: Body temperature, catalepsy, nociception, locomotive activity, light/dark transition, elevated plus maze, social interaction, prepulse inhibition, Y-maze, new object recognition, open field, chewing movement, vacuum chewing movement or oral dyskinesia, discriminatory prevention duty with

Figure 1 - Flow diagram of the study search process.

Source: Flow Chart Prism

positive maze, contextual fear conditioning, T-maze, passive avoidance, fear memory, Prepulse inhibition; Fear conditioning and Acute $\Delta 9$ -tetrahydrocannabinol challenge. As well as other tests, as neuronal expression analysis, glial markers expression, c-Fos expression, Glycemia, triglycerides, dopamine and serotonin levels, BDNF levels, M1/M4R binding, ChAT protein expression, AChE protein expression, CB1R, GABAAR bindings and GAD67; NR1 and GluA1.

DISCUSSION

Schizophrenia is a syndrome composed of cognitive deficits and positive and negative symptoms. The treatment focus on the precocious and continuous use of antipsychotics drugs, and in the medication rehabilitation, but these drugs only show a good response to the positive symptoms, while the other symptoms must be treated with other pharmacies and psychosocial treatments (Norman *et al.*, 2017; Barnes *et al.*, 2020).

Approximately one-third of the patients with schizophrenia did not answer

to the antipsychotic medication. Besides that, studies have shown that these medications present collateral effects, such as high cardiac frequency, metabolic syndrome, weight gain and involuntary movements, such as shakings and tremor e rigidity, emphasizing the importance of new medication development, aiming to improve the life quality of these patients with minimum collateral effects (Stroup & Gray, 2018; Wilianto, 2019)

According to our research, a total of 18 articles were obtained, in which the objective was to study the use of cannabidiol in the treatment and prevention of schizophrenia.

STUDY MODEL FOR SCHIZOPHRENIA

As we can observe, the selected articles in our studies used different schizophrenia induction models, being the most used the one of induction by MK-801, an NMDA receptor antagonist, that clinically induced psychosis and cognitive, sensory and motor deficits, similar to those observed in schizophrenia, besides that it induces hyperactivity, which was correlated with

Table 2 - Selected articles

Study	Animal Models	SCH Model	Tests
Levin <i>et al.</i> , 2014	Male Wistar Rats (aged 5 months) and Male SHR Rats (aged 5 months)	SHR Rats	IPP
Gomes <i>et al.</i> , 2015a	Male C57BL/6j Mice (aged 6 weeks)	Intraperitoneal administration of MK-801 (1 mg/kg) or SAL for 28 days	IPP
Gomes, <i>et al.</i> , 2015b	Male C57BL/6j Mice (aged 6 weeks)	Intraperitoneal administration of MK-801 (1 mg / kg) for 28 days	SI NOR EPM OF
Deiana <i>et al.</i> , 2015	Male Wistar Rats (aged 5 weeks)	Intraperitoneal administration of MK801 (0,08 mg/kg) or vehicle	SI in rats measured in a three-chamber apparatus
Sonego <i>et al.</i> , 2016	Male Swiss Mice (aged 6 weeks)	Bilateral or intra dorsal striatum	Catalepsy induced by haloperidol test
Peres <i>et al.</i> , 2018	Male Wistar Rats (aged 1 month) and Male SHR Rats (aged 1 month)	SHR Rats	Locomotor activity SI IPP Contextual Fear Conditioning
Stark <i>et al.</i> , 2019	Male Sprague-Dawley Rats	Intraperitoneal administration of MAM (22 mg/kg) or vehicle in GD17 day	OF SI NOR
Osborne <i>et al.</i> , 2019b	Puppy Sprague-Dawley Female Rats	Received an intravenous injection of either poly I:C or saline solution at gestation day 15	T-MAZE NOR SI
Silva <i>et al.</i> , 2020	Male C57BL/6j mice (aged 6 weeks).	Received intraperitoneal injections of saline or MK-801 (0.25, 0.5, or 1 mg/kg) twice a day for 7 days or 14 days	SI NOR
Kruk-Slomka & Biala, 2021	Male Swiss mice (aged 4 weeks)	Intraperitoneal administration of MK-801 (0.6 mg)	PA Locomotor Activity
Visini <i>et al.</i> , 2022	Male Nrg1 TM HET mice (aged 21-30 days)	Nrg1 TM HET mice	OF SI PPI FC

Label: EPM: elevated plus maze, OF: open-field, LD: Light-dark test, SI (Social interaction), NOR: New object recognition, IP: Intraperitoneal, CIOZ: Clonazepine, RIMO: rimonabat, HAL: Haloperidol, ARI: Aripiprazole, MAM: metilazoximetanolo acetate, GD: gestational day. PA :Passive avoidance test, PPI:Prepulse inhibition, FC:Fear conditioning.

psychomotor agitation in schizophrenic patients and disturbance of the prepulse inhibition of the surprising response system (Lefevre, 2016; Winship *et al.*, 2019)

Another model that is quite used was the

use of SHR, that shows impaired social interaction and hyperlocomotion when compared to Wistar rats, simulating negative and positive symptoms and a deficit in conditioning contextual fear and the prepulse inhibition test can be attenuated

Table 3- Biochemical tests of the selected articles

Study/Ref	Animal models	Schizophrenia model	Other tests
Gomes <i>et al.</i> , 2015a	Brain of male C57BL/6j mice (aged 6 weeks)	Intraperitoneal administration of MK-801 (1 mg / kg) for 28 days	Immunohistochemical of FosB / ΔFosB and parvalbumin (PV) Expression of the NMDAR GluN1 subunit gene by RT-PCR
Gomes <i>et al.</i> , 2015b	Brain of male C57BL/6j mice (aged 6 weeks)	Intraperitoneal administration of MK-801 (1 mg / kg) for 28 days	Immunohistochemical of expression of neuronal (Neon) and glial markers (astrocytes and microglia)
Sonego <i>et al.</i> , 2016	Brain of male Swiss mice (aged 6 weeks)	Bilateral or intra dorsal striatus	Immunohistochemical of c-Fos
Peres <i>et al.</i> , 2018	Male Wistar and SHR rats (aged 1 month)	SHR Rats	Quantification of Dopamine, Serotonin, BDNF, Glycemia and Triglycerides Levels
Jimenez Naranjo <i>et al.</i> , 2019	Brain of puppy male and female Sprague-Dawley rats	Received an intravenous injection of either poly I:C or saline solution at gestation day 15	M1/M4R binding density, ChAT and AChE protein expression in the PFC and HPC of offspring
Stark <i>et al.</i> , 2019	Male Sprague-Dawley rats	Intraperitoneal administration of MAM (22 mg / kg) or vehicle in GD17 day	Cannabinoid CB1 receptors in the PFC Endocannabinoid (EC) levels in the PFC
Osborne <i>et al.</i> , 2019a	Brain of puppy males Sprague-Dawley rats	Received an intravenous injection of either poly I:C or saline solution at gestation day 15	CB1R binding NMDAR binding GABAAR binding
Osborne <i>et al.</i> , 2019b	Brain of puppy female Sprague-Dawley rats	Received an intravenous injection of either poly I:C or saline solution at gestation day 15	NMDAR binding GABAAR binding
Yisini <i>et al.</i> , 2022	Male Nrg1 TM HET mice (aged 21-30 days)	Nrg1 TM HET mice	Western blot for GAD67; NR1 e GluA1

Label: ClOZ: Clonazepine, RIMO: rimonabat, HAL: Haloperidol, ARI: Aripiprazole, MAM: Metilazoximetanol acetate, GD: gestational day, GAD67: glutamato descarboxilase 67.

with the administration of antipsychotics, which is possible to observe in psychotomimetic manipulations, that can potencialize the behavioral abnormalities exhibited by SHR and induces a behavioral phenotype similar to that of schizophrenia in Wistar rats as also seen in other animal models of disorders and also in human patients (Levin *et al.*, 2014; Niigaki *et al.*, 2019).

The model of prenatal immunological

challenge induced by polyriboinosinic polyribocytidylic acid (polyI: C)), a synthetic double-strand RNA that imitates a viral infection by activating toll-like receptors 3. This model resembles the neurobiology and etiology of schizophrenia in animals and has good predictive value with defects displayed in prepulse inhibition and cognition, impairment of locomotor activities, deficits in learning skills,

disregulation of neurotransmission and brain morphological abnormalities, being used to study new drugs, whether preventive or therapeutic (Reisinger *et al.*, 2015; Hui *et al.*, 2018; Chamera *et al.*, 2020)

Mutation in the transmembrane domain Neuregulin 1 (Nrg1 TM HET) is one of the models used to study schizophrenia, mainly brain functions and behavior. NRG1 mutant mice are hyper locomotive, hyper explorers, reduction in anxiety in OF, decreased in PPI, deficient fear-associated memory (Long *et al.*, 2010; Zieba *et al.*, 2019). One of the articles used the model of neurological development disturbance induced by mitotoxin, methylazoxymethanol acetate (MAM) in female rats on the 17th day of gestation, which results in anomalous DNA methylation, and ultimately, interferes in the neurogenesis of baby rats, which produces many characteristics consistent with schizophrenia deficits, being considered a model with a high degree of facial and constructive validity (Ratajczak *et al.*, 2015; Horska *et al.*, 2020)

BEHAVIOR TESTS

Relevant tests for the negative and cognitive symptoms of schizophrenia

The test of social interaction is considered a precious tool in screening tests for anxiolytic and antipsychotic substances (Mograb, 2019; Sampedro-Viana *et al.*, 2021), evaluates the memory of social recognition by exposing adult rats (residents) to two meetings of 5 minutes each with the same juvenile intruder or with different juveniles in which the interval between encounters is usually of 30 minutes (Hodges *et al.*, 2020). A study by Gururajan *et al.* (2012) with Sprague-Dawley rats using the model of schizophrenia induced by acute administration of MK-801, acute pretreatment with CBD dose 3 mg/kg normalized not only the social investigation behavior as well as increased beyond control levels. One study suggests that administering CBD (15,30 and 60 mg/kg) to mice had a positive effect by reducing the harmful effects caused by MK-801, thus lessening the deficits seen during the SI and NOR test (Silva *et al.*, 2020).

In a study by Osborne *et al.* (2019a), the chronic administration of 21 days where 2 applications of CBD were performed daily with a dose of 10 mg also reversed the social interaction in female Sprague Dawley rats with poly 1:C

schizophrenia induction model. Furthermore, it is interesting to point out that in this study; the control feminine offspring with the administration of CBD had a lower interaction time compared to the control offspring with vehicle administration, suggesting that the administration of CBD impaired social interaction in healthy rats.

Curiously, in some studies, despite not having significant effects in SHR, the study by Almeida *et al.* (2013) with acute treatment of CBD (1 mg/kg) increased the total social interaction and the passive interaction in Wistar rats. The same occurred with Peres *et al.* (2018) in which the chronic administration of doses of 1 mg/kg, as well as 5 mg/kg, increased the social interaction in Wistar rats, but not in SHR. Given that social interaction can be modulated in Wistar rats by the administration of anxiolytic or anxiogenic compounds and that the CBD presents an anxiolytic profile, it could have interfered with the results, thus modifying anxiety levels (Hodges *et al.*, 2020).

In a study by Deiana *et al.* (2015) in the social interaction test in Wistar rats in a three-chamber device, the CBD (12 and 30 mg/kg) did not rescue MK-801 deficits and when it was combined with a protective dose of aripiprazole, the psychotic's benefit was lost. However, both in the study by Stark *et al.* (2019) with a dose of 30 mg/kg of CBD in chronic treatment in Sprague-Dawley rats with MAM-induced schizophrenia as in the study by Gomes *et al.* (2015a) in the chronic treatment with CBD in C57BL/6 mice with MK-801-induced schizophrenia with doses of 20 mg/kg as the dose of 60 mg/kg reversed the impaired social interaction.

Although it was observed that the CBD reversed the social interaction in these studies, it was also obtained studies in which the doses of CBD did not reverse the damage of the induced models of schizophrenia such as the studies by Long *et al.* (2010), Gururajan *et al.* (2011), neither of them obtained effects.

The new object recognition test evaluates the recognition memory of objects, that is, the ability to distinguish objects that have been previously presented (Lueptow, 2017). The study developed by Gomes (2015b) with the administration of MK-801 (1 mg/kg) for 28 days in C57BL/6j mice inducing a loss in performance in the new object recognition test. The CBD treatment of 30 mg/kg and 60 mg/kg was carried out for 22 days, but only the dose of 60 mg/kg attenuated the effect of

MK-801 significantly. As observed, both the dose of 30 mg/kg of CBD and the dose of 10 mg/kg dose reversed the deficits in recognition memory.

The Y-maze test evaluates the performance of the animals' working memory by assessing the spontaneous alternation behavior of the enumerated arms (1, 2 and 3) of the Y-maze, during a single session (D'isa *et al.*, 2021; Cleal *et al.*, 2021). The cerebral region of the prefrontal cortex has a fundamental role in working memory, so it is necessary to use it in the evaluation of schizophrenia to check cognitive symptoms (Smith *et al.*, 2018). In the study by Long *et al.* (2010), the chronic administration of CBD did not show a significant effect.

The light-dark test (LD) is based on the innate aversion that rodents have for illuminated areas, to access the anxiolytic properties of certain drugs. In the study by Long *et al.* (2010), only the dose of 1 mg/kg in chronic administration showed a significant effect.

Cannabidiol has not shown to have significant effects in the Y-maze test, which evaluates the attention and the memory using the T-maze as also the elevated plus maze (EPM) (Long *et al.*, 2010; Gomes *et al.*, 2015b; Osborne *et al.*, 2019a).

Tests that predict the effectiveness of antipsychotic drugs

The prepulse inhibition test (IPP) evaluates the sensory-motor response by the acoustic startle response, exploring the information processing deficits that normally occur in patients with schizophrenia (Yang *et al.*, 2017). Normally, the unexpected high stimuli elicit a startle response; however, if that sudden intense and surprising stimulus (pulse) is preceded by a weaker and not surprising sensory stimulus (prepulse), the startle response will be inhibited (Miller *et al.*, 2021). In schizophrenic patients, it is observed a deficit in the IPP, which exhibits the surprising response even when the pulse is preceded by the weak stimulus (Mena *et al.*, 2016; San-Martin *et al.*, 2020).

In the study by Long *et al.* (2010) in CB57/6 mice with MK-801-induced model of schizophrenia, both acute treatment with doses of 1, 5, and 50 mg/kg of CBD and chronic treatment with a dose of 1 mg/kg attenuated the deficits caused by the MK-801.

The study by Levin *et al.* (2014) in SHR and Wistar rats demonstrated that the administration

of the acute dose of 30 mg/kg of CBD was effective to attenuate the deficits in SHR. However, in the study by Gomes *et al.* (2015a), only the chronic treatment with doses of 30 mg/kg and 60 mg/kg of CBD attenuated the impairment in IPP induced by repeated treatment with MK-801 for 28 days. In a more current study of 2018, the chronic treatment with CBD 0,5 mg/kg prevented the emergence of IPP impairments in SHR (Peres *et al.*, 2018).

The conditioned fear test evaluates the neuronal processes that involve the acquisition, consolidation, and evocation of memory, considering that learning occurs in a single training session and can last for months (Shoji *et al.*, 2014). In the study of Kruk-Slomka & Biala (2021), confirmed that the acute injection of CBD (dose of 30 mg/kg) improved the acquisition, consolidation and recovery of long-term fear memory in the Passive avoidance test in mice, without affecting locomotor activity. However, the study concluded that CBD at non-effective doses (1 and/or 5 mg/kg) influencing only memory showed visible effects in reducing long-term fear memory impairment, but had no effect on the early memory formation memory fear in the PA test.

In the study by Visini *et al.* (2022), CBD (30 mg/kg) was not effective in reversing the relevant behaviors of schizophrenia caused by the Nrg1 mutation in mice. However, CBD increased locomotion and social behaviors. Furthermore, CBD had a positive effect on startle habituation, which is impaired in Nrg1 mutants.

A study by Levin *et al.* (2012), using Wistar rats and SHRs with the objective of evaluating both the effect of cannabidiol and the effect of rimonabant, a CB1 receptor antagonist, demonstrated that SHR presented a decrease in response to freezing when compared to Wistar rats which were attenuated by 1 mg/kg of CBD. In another study by Peres *et al.* (2018), the treatment with CBD of 0,5 mg/kg decreased the conditioning response to contextual fear showed by SHRs. According to the author, this answer is closely linked to regions of the amygdala and the hypothalamus (Esperidião-Antonio *et al.*, 2008).

The analysis of the animal's motor activity in the open field test acts as an indicator of the emotional state. The analysis of the animal's motor activity in the open field test acts as an indicator of the emotional state. According to Gobira *et al.* (2013), hyperlocomotion induced

by certain drugs in experimental animals may be representative of the positive symptoms of schizophrenia. The chronic administration of a dose of 50 mg/kg in C57BL/6 mice demonstrated to reduce the hyperlocomotion effect by MK-801 in the study by Long *et al.* (2010), the same result was not observed by the acute administration of CBD. It was also observed in the study by Peres *et al.* (2018) that the dose of 0,5 mg/kg of CBD in chronic administration prevented the hyperlocomotion in SHRs. Regarding acute administration, the pre-treatment with a dose of 3 mg/kg of CBD, demonstrated to inhibit the hyperlocomotion effect caused by MK-801. Therefore, it is noteworthy that despite being acute or chronic administration, the CBD managed to reverse the deficits of the schizophrenia models in these studies, however, the same result was not observed in the studies by Gururajan *et al.* (2012), Gomes *et al.* (2015b), and Stark *et al.* (2019).

Tests that predict the side effects of antipsychotics

The catalepsy test is frequently used in drug screening to assess the responsibility of potential antipsychotics for inducing extrapyramidal side effects, the test consists of measuring the latency period for the animal to withdraw from an unusual and uncomfortable posture (Luciani *et al.*, 2020). Only in the study by Sonogo *et al.* (2016), all the tested doses of CBD (15 mg/kg, 30 mg/kg, and 60 mg/kg) reduced the haloperidol-induced catalepsy when assessed at 1 and 2 hours, and also demonstrated that the 60 mg/kg dose attenuated haloperidol-induced catalepsy 30 minutes after the application of haloperidol. Other studies have shown that CBD had no significant effect (Peres *et al.*, 2018; Long *et al.*, 2010).

The oral dyskinesia test assesses the presence of orofacial dyskinesias that manifest as empty chewing movements, important to analyze the responsibility of potential antipsychotics to induce tardive dyskinesia or acute extrapyramidal side effects, clinically relevant due to its high prevalence, its impact on the quality of life and the fact that it persists even after discontinuation of treatment (Loughlin *et al.*, 2019; Patterson-Lomba *et al.*, 2019). The study by Peres *et al.* (2018) demonstrated that CBD did not induce oral dyskinesia.

Biochemical tests

In schizophrenic patients, post-mortem evidence

of abnormalities such as changes in neurons of aminobutyric acid (GABA) was observed, as well as in other indexes related to GABA-mediated neurotransmission (De Jonge *et al.*, 2017; Atagün, 2017; Kumar *et al.*, 2021), changes in the gene expression of the NR2B and NR1 subunits of the NMDA receptor (Lee & Zhou, 2019; Adell & Brain, 2020), as also changes in GluN1 subunit mRNA expression (Yuan *et al.*, 2018; Liu *et al.*, 2020).

Regarding the NMDA receptors, it was observed that the dose of 10 mg/kg of CBD attenuated the deficits caused by the poly (I:C)-induced model in the study by Osborne *et al.* (2019b) in female Sprague-Dawley rats, the same was not observed in the study by Osborne *et al.* (2019a) with male rats, demonstrating that depending on the gender, different results can be obtained and the importance of having more studies with females.

In analysis made by Long *et al.* (2010), the chronic treatment of MK-801 reduced the number of parvalbumin-positive (PV) cells in the medial prefrontal cortex and the NMDAR subunit gene (GluN) mRNA levels in the hippocampus that was attenuated by the treatment with 60 mg/kg of CBD. Moreover, the same study was observed that the dose of CBD (60 mg/kg) blocked the increase of FosB / Δ FosB in mPFC, but did not modify the increase of FosB / Δ FosB in the NAC nucleus of which the author reports that "CBD exhibits a profile similar to clozapine from a phenotypic point of view, but the mechanisms involved can be quite different". In Sonogo *et al.* (2016) immune histochemistry analysis was also performed for c-Fos in which the effect of haloperidol was attenuated by acute treatment with a dose of 30 mg/kg of CBD.

The CBD demonstrated to attenuate the deficits of poly (I:C) and MAM in the binding of the CB1 cannabinoid receptor in the prefrontal cortex at doses of 10 mg/kg and 30 mg/kg (Stark *et al.*, 2019; Osborne *et al.*, 2019b). Furthermore, the modification at the level of CB1 cannabinoid receptor coincided with negative and cognitive symptoms in MAM rats in the Stark *et al.* (2019) study in which the author confirms that it demonstrates the translational validity of the model as well as the CBD can have a protective effect against the model induced by MAM.

In schizophrenia, the role of dopamine and serotonin is widely studied, mainly because the blockade of dopamine D2 receptors is the

essential mechanism of antipsychotic activity and also that some antipsychotic effects may be due, at least in part, to its binding to several 5-HT receptors, especially 5-HT_{2A} and 5-HT_{1A} (Xia *et al.*, 2018; Kesby *et al.*, 2018; Wulff *et al.*, 2019; Chen *et al.*, 2021; Kim, 2021). The chronic treatment with a dose of 0,5 mg/kg of CBD increased the proportion of 5-HIAA/serotonin in both strains exhibited increased levels of dopamine and treatment with CBD increased levels of 5-HIAA, suggesting a possible involvement in the serotonergic system.

In the study by Gomes *et al.* (2015b) of which he analyzed the expression of glial markers such as astrocytes, GFAP and Iba-1 microglia by immunohistochemistry, considered more effective, glial changes by MK-801 were mitigated by repeated treatment with a dose of 60 mg/kg of CBD and Clozapine, however, Clozapine was considered more effective. Furthermore, in the study by Jimenez Naranjo *et al.* (2019) that analyzed the binding density of M1/MR4 and the expression of ChAT protein demonstrated that the 10 mg/kg dose of CBD reduced the density of M1/MR4 in the prefrontal cortex and subregions of the hippocampus in control animals and that the expression of ChAT protein was reduced in the hippocampus of male poly (I:C) offspring, whereas CBD treated poly (I:C) offspring exhibited levels of ChAT control.

CONCLUSION

It was observed that among the schizophrenia induction models used by the selected studies, it is still necessary to have further studies to validate the models. However, among these studies, the one that demonstrated to have validity was the MAM model. Cannabidiol has shown in both behavioral and biochemical tests to have an antipsychotic effect, acting differently compared to other antipsychotics, especially in higher doses as the doses of 30 and 60 mg/kg, however, further studies are needed to understand the possible mechanism of action of these effects.

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